

IMPACT OF FOREIGN INVESTMENTS ON ECONOMIC STABILITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11044580>

In today's modern world, foreign investments are given significant importance on a global scale. Foreign investments bring a flow of capital and advanced technologies to a country, thereby improving its economic condition. Consequently, the demand for foreign investments is particularly high in developing countries. In this context, a series of reforms aimed at enhancing the investment attractiveness and creating a favorable investment environment are being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The importance of the topic is evidenced by the specific definitions provided for foreign investments and foreign investors in The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities" of December 25, 2019, LRU-598[1], which clearly defines the activities and rights of foreign investors. In recent years, Uzbekistan has implemented reforms such as liberalizing the currency market and establishing special economic zones with tax incentives for investors, making the country an attractive destination for international capital. According to the Institute of Macroeconomic and Regional Studies (IMRS), Uzbekistan attracted \$7.5 billion in direct foreign investments during the first nine months of 2023. The main countries investing in Uzbekistan are China (accounting for over 65% of the shares), South Korea, Russia, Kazakhstan, and Turkey[2] and the primary sectors receiving investments are energy, metallurgy, and the chemical industry[3].

Figure 1. Investments in fixed capital per capita by region in the Republic of Uzbekistan [4]

According to a report by the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, from 2000 to 2022, among the 14 regions of the republic, Tashkent city attracted the most investments. In 2022, investments in fixed capital per capita amounted to 19539,3762975184 thousand soums.

In addition to the above statistical data, considering that Tashkent city is the smallest region in the country but has a population greater than the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Navoiy, Bukhara, Jizzakh, Surkhandarya, Khorezm, and Syrdarya regions[5], it is evident that it has rapidly developed into a well-established and investment-rich economic area. Numerous reforms are ongoing in other regions of the Republic to further improve the economic situation and increase investment attractiveness. In this regard, Uzbekistan offers:

- abundant and diverse natural resources (gas, gold, cotton, hydropower potential);
- low levels of debt and favorable foreign currency reserves;
- a substantial state investment program;
- a significant domestic market size (36 million people);
- a strategic position between China and Europe (“New Silk Road”);
- direct access to markets across Central Asia;
- a young and affordable workforce;
- tax incentives and subsidies attracting foreign investors’ attention.

Overall, foreign investments positively impact the economic stability of a country. Based on our research, we can state that foreign investments are necessary for Uzbekistan and that efforts to attract them are rapidly increasing.

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